

Studies on Benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazoles. Formation Constants of the Copper Chelates

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A potentiometric study on the complex formation of Cu^{II} with 2-benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazole (RH) in water-acetone (1:1) at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1$) at $32 \pm 0.5^\circ$ has indicated formation of two complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{R})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2$. The successive formation constant values ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) are computed by graphical methods following the method of Irving and Rossotti. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are found to be 9.15 ± 0.03 and 4.30 ± 0.03 respectively. Two acid dissociation constant (k_2^* and k_1^*) of the species RH_2^+ have also been determined under identical conditions, and pk_2^* and pk_1^* values are found to be 4.80 ± 0.02 and 10.90 ± 0.02 , respectively.

SOME biologically important chelating agents containing both sulphonamido group and benzimidazole nucleus are previously reported^{1,2}. The present paper describes the formation of Cu^{II} chelates of 2-benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazole (RH).

Acid dissociation constants³ (k_2^* and k_1^*) of the protonated species RH_2^+ and formation constants (K_1 and K_2) of the complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{R})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R})_2$, respectively have been determined potentiometrically following Irving and Rossotti titration technique⁴ in water-acetone (1:1) at $32 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in presence of requisite amount of KNO_3 to maintain ionic strength, $\mu=0.1$.

Experimental

The ligand (RH) was prepared and purified from benzenesulphonylglycine and *o*-phenylenediamine following a method previously described^{1,2}. All reagents were either of A.R. quality or properly purified. Their solutions were made in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified⁵ acetone.

pH measurements were made with a Elico LI-10T pH meter using glass electrode, calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solutions in water with due temperature correction.

Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml portion in (1:1) water-acetone of the following mixtures. (A) 0.02 M HNO_3 ; (B) 0.02 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01$ M RH, HNO_3 ; (C) 0.02 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01$ M RH, $\text{HNO}_3 + 1 \times 10^{-3}$ M or 5×10^{-4} M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ against 0.1 M KOH solution in water-acetone (1:1) were carried out at $32 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Ionic strength of the medium was kept constant ($\mu=0.1$) throughout by adding requisite amount of KNO_3 . Duplicate titration was made in each case under identical conditions. Titration curves pH vs volume of alkali solution added, were plotted.

Results

The acid dissociation of the protonated species RH_2^+ may be represented as

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), the average number of protons ($\bar{n}_H$) associated with the (R^-) have been calculated using the relation of Irving

Fig. 1. Titration curves: (I) 0.02 M HNO_3 , (II) 0.02 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01$ M RH_2^+ , (III) 0.02 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01$ M $\text{RH}_2^+ + 5 \times 10^{-4}$ M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (IV) 0.02 M $\text{HNO}_3 + 0.01$ M $\text{RH}_2^+ + 1 \times 10^{-3}$ M $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

and Rossotti. The evaluation of pk_2^* and pk_1^* have been made by linear-plots on assumption that

$[R^-] \approx 0$ when $1 > \bar{n}_H > 2$, and $[RH_2^+] \approx 0$ when $0 < \bar{n}_H < 1$.

The $\bar{n}_H$ values have also been calculated using the experimentally determined values of k_2^* and k_1^* from equation (3)

$$\bar{n}_{H(\text{calcd.})} = \frac{2[H^+]^2/k_1^*k_2^* + [H^+]/k_1^*}{[H^+]^2/k_1^*k_2^* + [H^+]/k_1^* + 1} \quad (3)$$

The standard deviation (σ) has been calculated⁴ using equation (4).

$$\sigma = \pm \left\{ \frac{\sum [\bar{n}_{H(\text{calcd.})} - \bar{n}_{H(\text{exptl.})}]^2}{\text{Number of observations}} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

The limits of error of the constant values are obtained from the maximum horizontal displacement of the calculated curves ($\bar{n}_{H(\text{calcd.})}$ vs pH) from the experimental one. Results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF RH_2^+ AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF ITS Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

RH_2^+ $Cu(R)_2$	pK_1^* 4.80 ± 0.02	pK_2^* 10.9 ± 0.02	$\log K_1$ 9.15 ± 0.03	$\log K_2$ 4.80 ± 0.03
	$\sigma = \pm 0.014$ (0 < $\bar{n}$ < 1.8)		$\sigma = \pm 0.014$ (0 < $\bar{n}$ < 1.8)	

The stepwise formation of Cu^{II} complex with protonated species RH_2^+ may be represented as

From the titration curves, the average number ($\bar{n}$) of ligand (R^-) bound to Cu^{II} and free ligand exponent pL ($L=R^-$) are evaluated using the relations of Irving and Rossotti⁴.

On plotting $\bar{n}$ vs pL , one may obtain formation curve, and the successive formation constant, K_1 and K_2 have been evaluated by the linear plot of equation (7).

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(2-\bar{n})L^2} = \frac{(1-\bar{n})}{(2-\bar{n})L} \times K_1 + K_1K_2 \quad (7)$$

The above relation reduces to

$$pL = \log \frac{1-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}} + \log K_1, \text{ assuming } [M(R)_2] \approx 0 \text{ when}$$

$$0 < \bar{n} < 1, \text{ and } pL = \log \frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1} + \log K_2, \text{ assuming}$$

$$[M^{2+}] \approx 0 \text{ when } 1 < \bar{n} < 2 \text{ (equation 8)}$$

The $\bar{n}$ values have been calculated from equation (9) using experimentally determined values of K_1 and K_2

$$\bar{n} (\text{calcd.}) = \frac{K_1L + 2K_1K_2L^2}{1 + K_1L + K_1K_2L^2} \quad (9)$$

The calculated formation curve has been drawn along with the experimental points. Standard deviation and limits of error have also been determined⁴. Results are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

The method of Irving and Rossotti has been employed to determine the dissociation constant, k_2^* and k_1^* of the ligand RH_2^+ , and formation constant, K_1 and K_2 of its Cu^{II} complexes. The pK_2^* and pK_1^* values are found to be 4.80 ± 0.02 and 10.90 ± 0.02 , respectively, of which the first one is obviously due to deprotonation of benzimidazolium ion and the second is due to dissociation of imdohydrogen of $-SO_2NH-$ group.

The study indicates that RH_2^+ may act as diprotic bidentate ligand in the complex formation with Cu^{II} . The standard deviation was found to be ± 0.014 in the region $0 < \bar{n} < 1.8$.

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References

1. N. N. GHOSH and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 517.
2. N. N. GHOSH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 1909.
3. N. N. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 568.
4. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", E.L.B.S., London, 1956, p. 171.
6. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3897.
7. F. J. O. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw-Hill, London, 1961, p. 88.